

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE PERSONNEL TRAINING SYSTEM FOR THE PUBLIC SECURITY SERVICE OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract: This article discusses the distinctive features of the personnel training system for the public security service of internal affairs bodies, with the author providing suggestions and recommendations.

Keywords: Internal affairs bodies, public security, service, personnel training, system.

During the years of independence, Uzbekistan has established a completely new system for ensuring public safety, which has its own scientific-theoretical, legal, and organizational-tactical foundations. Throughout the independence period, a comprehensive legal system has been created in the country to protect the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, maintain public order, ensure the safety of individuals, society, and the state, and prevent offenses.[1]

The internal affairs bodies are a specially authorized system with the primary forces and means of ensuring public safety. In accordance with the Action Strategy, fundamental reforms have been carried out to transform it into a people-oriented system.

Taking into account modern risks and threats, as well as the importance and scale of the work being carried out, systematic organizational measures are being implemented to clearly define and allocate the tasks and functions of internal affairs units at all levels, optimize the organizational and staffing structure, and rationally use forces and resources. As a result, by optimizing the organizational structure and tasks of all branches of the internal affairs bodies, 85% of employees now work in the lower-level system.[2] To create a safe, crime-free environment within the mahalla itself, a prevention inspector was established in each mahalla based on the concept of "Prosperous and Safe Mahalla." [3] In order to create a safe, crime-free environment in the mahalla itself, a prevention inspector was established in each mahalla based on the concept of "Prosperous and Safe Mahalla." [3]

A system of regular reporting to the public by officials at all levels of the internal affairs bodies has been implemented, as well as new mechanisms for public, parliamentary, and deputy oversight to ensure legality in their activities, thus ensuring the openness and transparency of the system's operations.[4]

To ensure systematic dialogue with the people, social partnership with civil society institutions, and comprehensive assistance in solving the most critical problems of the population, a system is being developed to address issues directly on-site by identifying and eliminating the causes of crimes at the level of each mahalla, family, and individual.

A system of "mahalla-by-mahalla," door-to-door, "family-by-family," and "citizen-by-citizen" work has been introduced for internal affairs bodies across different sectors. Prevention inspectors and women's affairs inspectors are actively involved in creating "Iron Notebooks," "Women's Notebooks," and "Youth Notebooks" in mahallas, as well as in addressing the problems of citizens included in them.[5]

Units for handling appeals from individuals and legal entities have been established at all levels of internal affairs bodies. The "E-Murojaat" electronic system has been implemented in the activities of internal affairs bodies, establishing a qualitatively new procedure for receiving, considering, and resolving appeals, as well as monitoring these processes.

The effectiveness of the reforms being carried out in our country today is primarily directly linked to expanding the ranks of young personnel with high spiritual values, independent thinking, and the ability to take responsibility for the fate and future of our Motherland.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasizes that since the early years of independence, priority has been given to ensuring security and stability in our country and maintaining public order. This is reflected in the reorganization of preventive, operational-search, investigation, road safety, fire safety, security, patrol and post services, and mobilization units performing special tasks, as well as the continuous strengthening of the material and technical base of internal affairs bodies.

The emerging threats and dangers in the world, primarily international terrorism, religious extremism, illegal migration, human trafficking, and the increasing spread of ideas alien to our people among youth, are presenting new tasks for internal affairs bodies to prevent and eliminate them in a timely manner.

In this regard, the President of the country, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, expressed his opinion that serious shortcomings and problems accumulated in the activities of internal affairs bodies in recent years are hindering the effective implementation of these tasks. Specifically:

First, the lack of clear distribution of main tasks and functions among republican, middle, and lower-level units makes it difficult to determine the priorities of each employee's activities and personal responsibility for the final result of work;

Second, the existing organizational and staffing structures do not ensure the rational use of forces and resources, resulting in some central and middle-level services maintaining excessive staff units despite insufficient workload, while imposing excessive service responsibilities on subordinate units;

Third, the dialogue between officials of internal affairs bodies, including prevention inspectors, and the population is not established, the culture of communication with citizens remains poor, and effective cooperation with citizens' self-government bodies and other civil society institutions is not ensured in solving the most pressing problems of the population;

Fourth, appeals from individuals and legal entities are considered superficially, the issues raised in them are not comprehensively and deeply analyzed, and the fact that responses to appeals are given merely for formality causes dissatisfaction among citizens, forcing them to appeal to the People's Receptions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other organizations;

Fifth, an effective system of accountability for officials of internal affairs bodies to the population and effective mechanisms of public, parliamentary, and deputy control over their activities have not been introduced, which does not allow for increasing employees' responsibility for the effective performance of assigned tasks;

Sixth, work on preventing offenses mainly consists of combating the consequences of committed illegal acts, while systematic and effective measures are not taken to prevent

offenses, deeply analyze, identify, and eliminate the causes and conditions for their commission;

Seventh, insufficient attention is paid to protecting the younger generation from destructive ideas, preventing the involvement of youth in criminal activities, primarily terrorism and religious extremism, and the educational role of internal affairs bodies is not felt;

Eighth, the system of training, retraining, and professional development of internal affairs bodies' employees does not meet current requirements, and cases of bribery and abuse of official position still occur;

Ninth, the level of implementation of the latest information and communication technologies in the system and the equipping of internal affairs bodies with modern tools and equipment remains unsatisfactory[9].

Based on these issues, the head of our state identified the following key areas for reforming the system of internal affairs bodies:

First, transforming the internal affairs bodies into a socially oriented professional structure that provides timely and quality assistance to the population, where each employee considers "serving the interests of the people" as their duty;

Second, clearly defining and allocating tasks and functions of internal affairs units at all levels, taking into account modern risks and threats, the importance and scale of the work being carried out, optimizing the organizational and staffing structure, and rationally using forces and resources;

Third, ensuring purposeful systemic dialogue with the people, developing close cooperation with citizens' self-government bodies and other civil society institutions, and providing comprehensive assistance in solving the most pressing problems of the population;

Fourth, establishing a qualitatively new procedure for handling appeals from individuals and legal entities, putting an end to superficial and formalistic approaches to considering and resolving appeals, and utilizing all means within their authority to protect the rights and legitimate interests of citizens;

Fifth, introducing a system of regular reporting by officials of internal affairs bodies to the population, clear criteria for evaluating work done, as well as effective mechanisms of public, parliamentary and deputy oversight to ensure legality in their activities;

Sixth, primarily ensuring early prevention of offenses by timely eliminating the causes and conditions for their commission, raising the legal culture of all segments of the population, instilling in them respect for the law and intolerance to any manifestation of law violation;

Seventh, educating minors and youth in the spirit of love for the Motherland, patriotism, respect for national and universal values, developing a system aimed at protecting the younger generation from ideas of terrorism, religious extremism, violence and cruelty;

Eighth, fundamentally revising and further improving the system of training, retraining and professional development of internal affairs personnel, eliminating the causes and conditions leading to their commission of offenses;

Ninth, widely introducing modern information and communication technologies to ensure more effective activities of all departments of internal affairs bodies;

Tenth, further improving the material and technical support for the activities of internal affairs bodies, creating decent conditions for the effective work of employees, and providing them with official housing.

Over the past period, large-scale reforms have been carried out to improve the system of internal affairs bodies. In particular, significant work has been done on developing and strengthening the lower level of internal affairs bodies organized to maintain public order, ensure citizen safety, prevent offenses and combat crime in mahallas.

Issues related to improving the professional and combat training of internal affairs personnel are of particular importance in the effective implementation of personnel policy. Internal affairs officers today face many non-standard situations, the resolution of which sometimes largely depends on their patriotism and professional skills, their ability to act in strict accordance with the law. The formation of these and other necessary qualities of internal affairs personnel should be ensured by an effective system of professional and combat training within the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

One of the most important measures to ensure public safety is providing personnel familiar with modern science and technology for this sphere to function based on specific mechanisms.

The reforms being implemented in this direction based on relevant presidential decrees include: firstly, organizing a system for training highly qualified specialists in public safety based on advanced international standards; secondly, increasing the personnel potential of units in this area, taking into account current demands; thirdly, ensuring professional growth of employees according to their qualifications; fourthly, further enhancing the intellectual and professional potential of managerial personnel in effectively managing forces and resources.

As a result of the reforms being implemented to improve the system of training personnel for public safety activities, firstly, as a result of the fundamental reform of the educational process of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the introduction of a two-level system of higher education (bachelor's and master's) and mechanisms for targeted training of personnel in the management structure, further increasing the intellectual and professional potential of leading personnel in the effective management of forces and means of public safety; secondly, the introduction of a continuous training system, including a procedure inextrica

The significance of reforms in this area lies in the fact that, based on modern requirements, the University of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established to enhance the personnel potential of law enforcement agencies and the Armed Forces.

The university has been designated as a basic higher military educational and research institution for the targeted training of qualified personnel. For the first time in the country's history, the University has created an opportunity for young people to study at a higher military educational institution on a civilian basis, and girls have been admitted to military education.

In conclusion, it can be said that as a result of reforms aimed at further improving the public safety system and increasing its effectiveness, the state of protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, the interests of society and the state from illegal encroachments will be raised to a qualitatively high level. In ensuring public safety, by directing the service activities

of employees to assist citizens, it is possible to increase the trust of the population in the competent state bodies for public safety.

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